

Maternal Mortality at a Tertiary Care Centre in Andhra Pradesh**Maganti Jyothi Sree¹, P. Sudha Padmasree², Dasari Mary Manjula³, Kodali Venkata Ramana⁴, C. Amulya⁵, Gunapalli kaivalya⁶**¹Postgraduate, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India.²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India.⁴Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India.⁵ Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India.⁶Intern, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Background:** The maternal mortality ratio is a significant public health indicator that reflects the quality of health care services. This study aimed to determine the maternal mortality ratio (MMR), identify various risk factors, and analyze the causes of maternal mortality.**Methods:** This is a prospective, observational hospital based study at a tertiary care center in Visakhapatnam from June 2022 to May 2023. The research analyzed the causes and contributing factors of each maternal death.**Results:** A total of 46 maternal deaths occurred during the study period, resulting in a mean MMR of 144 per 100,000 livebirths. Most maternal deaths (30.43%) occurred among women aged 13-19 years, with 56.52% occurring in multiparous women and 82.61% among unregistered patients. Direct causes accounted for 73.91% of the deaths, with hypertension (44.12%) and hemorrhage (26.47%) being the major contributors.**Conclusion:** Improving rural healthcare facilities, upgrading referral centers, and enhancing transport systems are essential to reduce maternal mortality.**Keywords:** Maternal Mortality Ratio, Maternal Death, Hypertensive Disorder, Haemorrhage, Sepsis.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

According to the International Classification of Diseases (ICD)-10, maternal death is defined as "the death of a woman while pregnant or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of the duration and site of the pregnancy, from any cause related to or aggravated by the pregnancy or its management but not from accidental or incidental causes" (World Health Organization, 1999).[1] The vast majority of these deaths (94%) occur in low-resource settings and are mostly preventable.[2] Improving maternal health is a key priority for the WHO. Globally, the MMR fell from 385 in 1990 to 216 per 100,000 livebirths in 2015, with significant variations across countries. The Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) target 3.1

aims to reduce the global MMR to less than 70 per 100,000 livebirths by 2030.[3]

Maternal mortality is a crucial health indicator for every country. Efforts to improve maternal outcomes can be achieved through antenatal and postpartum care programs focused on preventing and recognizing complications of pregnancy and childbirth. Maternal mortality has been an issue of concern in India for many years, and it is one of the six countries that contribute to 50% of the world's maternal mortality.[4] India has made significant progress, achieving a 77% decline in MMR between 1990 and 2016, with institutional births doubling from 38.7% in 2005 to 78.9% in 2015.[5,6] Despite the large gains made in terms of improved agency, education, employment, and fertility desires for women, most maternal deaths remain preventable and are largely clustered among

groups of socioeconomically disadvantaged women. Disease outbreaks, conflicts, and other public health emergencies exacerbate the situation by increasing the risk of pregnancy complications, disrupting healthcare systems, and posing additional constraints to maternal and perinatal healthcare. This study was conducted in a tertiary medical college hospital in Andhra Pradesh, which receives many referrals from surrounding rural areas. The objectives of the present study were to identify the risk factors and analyse the causes of maternal mortality.

Materials and Methods

The present study is a prospective, observational hospital based study conducted at King George Hospital, Visakhapatnam from June 2022 to May 2023. Large number of patients were referred from district hospitals, primary health centers, and

surrounding rural parts. The details of maternal deaths were collected and analysed with a view to identify the avoidable risk factors. Results obtained were tabulated and analysed using SPSS version 24.

Results

During the study period, 46 maternal deaths were recorded and the calculated mortality ratio (MMR) was 144 per 100,000. The demographic and socioeconomic distribution of 46 mothers were presented in Table 1. Maximum maternal deaths (30.43%) were reported in the age group of 13-19 years followed by 28.26% in woman above 35 years. Among 46 women, majority died (76.09%) during postpartum period and 10 woman (21.73%) died prior to delivery of the fetus during the antepartum and one (2.17%) during intrapartum period.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of maternal deaths (N=46)

Patient Characteristics				
Age (years)		Number	Percentage	
13-19		14	30.43	
20-25		9	19.57	
26-30		5	10.87	
31-35		5	10.87	
>35		13	28.26	
Timing of maternal death				
Antepartum		10	21.73	
Intrapartum		1	2.17	
Postpartum		35	76.09	
Parity				
Primiparous		20	43.48	
Para	1	2	4.35	} 56.52
	2	2	4.35	
	3	4	8.70	
	4	8	17.39	
	>4	10	21.74	
ANC				
Yes		8	11.39	
No		38	82.61	
Residence / Geographic location				
Rural		40	43.48	
Tribal / Hilly		22	47.82	
Urban		4	8.70	
Types of delay				
Delay in deciding to seek care		20	43.48	
Delay in reaching health care facilities		4	8.70	
Delay in receiving care		22	47.82	

More deaths were reported in multiparous woman (26/46; 56.52%) than primiparous (20/46; 43.48%). Among multiparous, woman with four or more parity had higher mortality rate (17.39 and 21.74 %). Only eight (17.39%) had regular antenatal check-ups while 38 (82.61%) had no proper

antenatal care. Majority of the maternal deaths were reported in women from rural areas (47.82%) followed by tribal and hilly areas (43.48%) and four (8.70%) were from urban areas.

Assessment of types of delays associated with maternal mortality showed that the majority of

deaths (47.82%) were associated with delay in decision to seek care or due to delay in reaching health care facility (43.48 %). Four women (8.70%) died due to delay in receiving treatment (Table 1).

Out of 46 deaths 52.17% were referred from PHC followed by 23.91% from CHC and AC whereas 13.04 and 10.87% were home deliveries and at tertiary hospitals (Fig 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of maternal mortality based on place of referral

In our study, 73.91% (34/46) of maternal deaths were due to direct causes. Hypertension, (44.12%), hemorrhage (26.47%), sepsis (23.53%) and rupture of uterus (5.88% were the major direct causes of

maternal deaths. The indirect causes were fever (25%), heart disease (33.33%) jaundice (16.67%) and tumor, anemia and CVA accounted for 8.33% each (Table 2).

Table 2: Causes of maternal mortality (N=46)

Direct causes (N=34)	Number	Percentage
Hypertensive disorders	24	52.17
Haemorrhage	11	23.91
Sepsis	5	10.87
Rupture of uterus	6	13.04
TOTAL	34	100.00
Indirect causes (N=12)		
Fever	3	25.00
Heart disease	4	33.33
Jaundice	2	16.67
Anemia	1	8.33
Tumour	1	8.33
CVA	1	8.33
TOTAL	12	100.00

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Discussion

A total of 46 maternal deaths were analyzed, focusing on age, antenatal care, parity, place of residence, cause of death, and delays in reaching the tertiary care center from primary care centers.

Most maternal deaths (30.43%) were reported among women aged 13-19 years, followed by 28.26% in women above 35years. This aligns with previous studies indicating that adolescent mothers had twice the risk of death compared to those in

their 20s, a situation linked to the custom of early marriage in rural areas.[7,8] The high maternal mortality observed among women above 35 years is consistent with findings by Nove et al. (2014),[9] who identified older maternal age as a high-risk factor. Conversely, studies by Mahala et al. (2017)[10] and Gaikwad et al. (2020)[11] reported that the majority of maternal deaths in Rajasthan and Maharashtra (47.4% and 46.03% respectively) had occurred in the 21-25 age group, highlighting regional differences.

Among the 46 women, the majority (76.09%) died during the postpartum period, with 10 women (21.73%) died prior to delivery and one (2.17%) during the intrapartum period. The high postpartum mortality observed aligns with studies by Yadav et al. (72.16%),[12] Bhatia et al. (77.77%)[13] and Gaikwad et al. (68.25%).[11] Risk factors for postpartum mortality included cesarean delivery, post-discharge complications, and shock upon admission.

In this study, most deaths occurred among multiparous women (56.52%), while 43.48% were among primiparous women. These findings are consistent with studies by Bhadra et al. (2020)[14] and Singh et al. (2022),[15] who reported high maternal mortality rates (74.28 % and 57.90%, respectively) among multiparous women, likely due to complications such as hypertension and anemia. Conversely, Yadav et al. (2018)[16] and Ganesh and Archana (2020)[17] recorded higher maternal mortality in primiparous women.

The study found that mortality was higher (82.61%) among women who had not received any antenatal supervision (unbooked), which aligns with previous observations.[14,17] The lower mortality observed among booked patients could be due to improved care and early detection or prevention of complications.

The death rate among mothers from rural and tribal/hilly areas (47.82% and 43.48%) was higher, likely due to lower access and utilization of health care services, lack of awareness, illiteracy, and poor socioeconomic status. Many deaths were associated with delays in deciding to seek care (47.82%) or in reaching health care facilities (43.48%). This underscores the need to strengthen healthcare workers capacity to recognize danger signs early and refer patients promptly.[18]

This study was conducted in a medical college hospital that receives referrals of complex and high-risk cases from lower-level facilities. Among the 46 deaths, 52.17% were referred from primary health centers (PHC), 23.91% from community health centers (CHC), and area hospitals (AH), while 13.04% and 10.87% occurred at home and tertiary hospitals, respectively. These cases often

involve severe complications, pre-existing medical conditions, or multiple complications that increase the risk of maternal death. Insufficient resources and a shortage of skilled staff at lower health facilities, as well as an inadequate referral system, could contribute to increased maternal mortality.[19,20]

Direct causes accounted for 73.91% of maternal deaths, while indirect causes accounted for 26.09%. Among the direct causes death due to hypertension (44.12%), hemorrhage including postpartum hemorrhage, antepartum hemorrhage and abortion related hemorrhage contribute to (26.47%), sepsis (Puerperal sepsis, antepartum sepsis and intrapartum sepsis) accounts for (23.53%) and rupture of uterus in 2 (5.88%) cases. Out of 12 deaths due to indirect causes, fever in (25%), heart disease (33.33%), jaundice (16.67%), tumour, anaemia and CVA in one patient each (8.33%) which were similar to that reported by the previous studies.

Chappell et al. (2021)[21] also reported hypertensive disorders of pregnancy as leading causes of maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality, affecting upto 10% of pregnancies worldwide. Ananth and Joseph (2021)[22] highlighted the impact of hypertension on increasing MMR in a 40-year sequential time series analysis in the United States. Meh et al. (2021)[23] documented that the leading causes of maternal death included obstetric hemorrhage (47%), pregnancy-related infection (12%), and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (7%).

The study observed that indirect causes of death accounted for 26.09% of maternal deaths, aligning with reports by Hossain and Shaikh (2022)[24] that indirect maternal deaths constitute one-quarter of total deaths. However, Epelboin et al. (2021)[25] reported that indirect causes, such as pre-existing medical conditions like HIV/AIDS and the COVID-19 pandemic, accounted for more than 70% of maternal deaths. These variations could result from differences in sociodemographic characteristics, the quality of health care provided, and health system performance between countries.

Conclusion

Maternal healthcare is a critical issue, with disparities in socioeconomic status, gender, ethnicity, education, place of residence, and age increasing the risk of death during pregnancy. There is significant potential for reducing maternal mortality, as most maternal deaths are preventable. Early detection of high-risk pregnancies and timely referral to tertiary centers can reduce complications associated with high-risk pregnancies.

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